

Small Inertial Sensors for a Miniature Autonomous Underwater Vehicle

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Abstract— Testing and algorithm development are addressed for the guidance system of a low-cost (disposable) miniature autonomous underwater vehicle. The requirements for low-cost and small size systems typically necessitate the use of low-performance sensors. In this work, we address the limitations of low-performance inertial sensors. Mechanized calibration routines are developed to compensate for high drift rates in gyro calibration coefficients, and compass/gyro stabilization methods are investigated to address susceptibility of the compass to magnetic interference.

I. INTRODUCTION

A miniature autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) has been designed and constructed at the United States Naval Academy to study the capabilities and engineering/cost requirements of very small AUVs. Our ultimate goal is to design an AUV that is small, easily deployable, and so inexpensive that it is considered expendable. To design a such a miniature AUV implies the use of inexpensive and low-accuracy guidance sensors. The focus of this paper is the testing, calibration, and development of guidance algorithms for the inexpensive guidance sensors chosen for our miniature AUV.

The miniature AUV is shown in Figure 1. It measures approximately 9 cm by 60 cm and displaces 3.28 kg. Our interest is in developing an inexpensive guidance system that can support short-duration dead reckoning, which will allow the AUV to navigate to the vicinity of an underwater target whose location is determined by a separate mothership-type vehicle.

II. VEHICLE GUIDANCE SENSORS

Heading rate is measured by a MicroGyro 100 solid state rate-gyro made by Gyration, and has a drift rate on the order of degrees per second. The MicroGyro 100 is a small and inexpensive analog output device, and is being marketed for computer-game controller applications. AUV magnetic heading is measured by a Vector 2XG electronic compass made by PNI Corporation. The compass has a serial output, resolution of 1 degree, and accuracy of 2 degrees RMS. The magnetic sensors on the compass are gim-

Fig. 1. The USNA miniature autonomous underwater vehicle.

bal mounted. Pitch and roll are both measured by Analog Devices single integrated circuit accelerometers with analog outputs. They resolve pitch and roll by measuring the gravity vector. The accelerometers also measure body acceleration — body acceleration cannot be distinguished from the gravity vector — and since the AUV is not a high performance vehicle, the accelerometer measurement is dominated by gravity. All analog sensor signals are sampled using 12-bit A/D conversion. The embedded controller for the miniature AUV is a Rabbit 2000 microprocessor made by Rabbit Semiconductor. The interior of the AUV is shown in Figure 2. A more complete description of the AUV is found in [8].

Fig. 2. Interior of mini-AUV 1.

A body-fixed coordinate system is attached to the miniature AUV with the origin at the center of gravity. The positive x -axis is directed through the nose of the AUV, the positive z -axis is directed down, and the y -axis completes a right-handed coordinate system [2]. The gyro is aligned with the z -axis of the AUV in order to assist in stabilizing heading measurements obtained by the compass. Since the compass is gimbal mounted, it returns heading measurements with respect to a local level navigation frame.

III. CALIBRATION

Our initial focus is on calibration of the gyro. Though there are a number of error sources that can be examined, such as acceleration-dependent biases, temperature dependent biases, and misalignment errors [7], we find that the low-precision gyro used here is dominated by two major error sources: scale-factor and bias error. Thus we assume the output of the gyro is written

$$r_m(t) = (1 + a)r(t) + b \quad (1)$$

where $r_m(t)$ is the measured value and $r(t)$ is the true angular rate about the z -axis. The coefficients a and b are the scale-factor and the bias errors, respectively.

We will often find it more convenient to express (1) as

$$r(t) = \bar{a}r_m(t) + \bar{b} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\bar{a} = \frac{1}{1+a}, \quad \bar{b} = \frac{-b}{1+a}$$

Measurements from the gyro and compass are combined to estimate the true heading of the miniature AUV. This is done in a standard manner by noting the integral relationship between the two sets of measurements,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\psi}(t) &= \frac{\cos \phi(t)}{\cos \theta(t)} (\bar{a}r_m(t) + \bar{b}) + v(t) \\ y(t) &= \psi(t) + w(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\psi(t)$ is the heading of the AUV, $y(t)$ is the output of the compass, $\phi(t)$ is the roll angle of the AUV (rotation about positive x -axis), $\theta(t)$ is the pitch angle (rotation about the positive y -axis), and $v(t)$ and $w(t)$ are additive Gaussian noise terms that somewhat loosely represent noise in both the gyro and compass measurements. For notational clarity, noise sources $v(t)$ and $w(t)$ will be suppressed in the sequel. The cosine terms in (3) are needed to map the body-fixed gyro measurement to the local-level compass measurement—recall the compass is gimbal mounted. Body-fixed y -axis angular rate also contributes to $\dot{\psi}(t)$ (see [7], p. 45), but its effect is minimal under a small roll-angle assumption. For the mini-AUV1, body-fixed y -axis angular rate is not instrumented, but roll-angle is statically stable

due to separation between center of gravity and center of buoyancy, so that body-fixed y -axis angular rate can be reasonably ignored in (3).

Since all estimation algorithms are implemented on the miniature AUV's embedded controller, we find it convenient to derive the algorithms for a discrete-time version of (3)

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(k+1) &= \psi(k) + h \frac{\cos \phi(k)}{\cos \theta(k)} (\bar{a}r_m(k) + \bar{b}) \\ y(k) &= \psi(k) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where h is the sample period.

A. Mechanized calibration

Proper biasing of the gyro is a crucial step in implementing the miniature AUV's guidance system. Through initial trials, we have found that biasing of the low-accuracy gyro is variable, and must be recomputed periodically. In this section, we present options for mechanizing the rate-gyro calibration that can be performed automatically and periodically as part of a standard mission profile.

A.1 Extended Kalman filter

A common approach to mechanized calibration (see [4] and [5]), is to augment (4) with additional states representing the calibration coefficients, and implement an extended Kalman filter to estimate values of \bar{a} and \bar{b} . Though this is a fairly common approach, we briefly show that it is not appropriate for the system at hand.

Augmenting (4) with additional states for the scale-factor and bias errors yields

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(k+1) &= \psi(k) + h (\bar{a}r_m(k) + \bar{b}) \\ \bar{a}(k+1) &= \bar{a}(k) \\ \bar{b}(k+1) &= \bar{b}(k) \\ y(k) &= \psi(k) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $y(k)$ is the output of the system, and we have simplified our analysis by assuming the AUV is level, $\phi = \theta = 0$. The extended Kalman filter requires that (5) is locally observable [3]. Linearization of (5) at an arbitrary equilibrium yields the linear system

$$\begin{aligned} z(k+1) &= Az(k) + Bu(k) \\ y(k) &= Cz(k) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & hr^o & h \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad C = [1 \ 0 \ 0],$$

z is state deviation vector, and r^o is a constant equilibrium value of the input. To see that (5) is not observable, it

suffices to verify

$$\text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} C \\ CA \\ CA^2 \end{bmatrix} = \text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & hr^o & h \\ 1 & 2hr^o & 2h \end{bmatrix} < 3$$

Thus an extended Kalman filter does not yield asymptotically correct values for the augmented states \bar{a} and \bar{b} .

A.2 On-line least squares

We adopt an alternate approach where a set of data is collected and a least squares problem is solved on-line to estimate \bar{a} and \bar{b} .

For any given initial index k and initial condition $\psi(k)$, we may write the output at any future index as

$$y(k+n) = \psi(k) + \bar{a}h \sum_{i=k}^{k+n-1} \frac{\cos \phi(i)}{\cos \theta(i)} r_m(i) + \bar{b}h \sum_{i=k}^{k+n-1} \frac{\cos \phi(i)}{\cos \theta(i)} \quad (6)$$

for $n > 0$. Rearranging and stacking (6) yields

$$z = Gq$$

where

$$z = \begin{bmatrix} y(k+1) - y(k) \\ y(k+2) - y(k) \\ \vdots \\ y(k+n) - y(k) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$q = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{a} \\ \bar{b} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$G = [G_1 \quad G_2]$$

and

$$G_1 = \begin{bmatrix} h \frac{\cos \phi(k)}{\cos \theta(k)} r_m(k) \\ h \sum_{i=k}^{k+1} \left(\frac{\cos \phi(i)}{\cos \theta(i)} r_m(i) \right) \\ \vdots \\ h \sum_{i=k}^{k+n-1} \left(\frac{\cos \phi(i)}{\cos \theta(i)} r_m(i) \right) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$G_2 = \begin{bmatrix} h \frac{\cos \phi(k)}{\cos \theta(k)} \\ h \sum_{i=k}^{k+1} \left(\frac{\cos \phi(i)}{\cos \theta(i)} \right) \\ \vdots \\ h \sum_{i=k}^{k+n-1} \left(\frac{\cos \phi(i)}{\cos \theta(i)} \right) \end{bmatrix}$$

The least square estimates of \bar{a} and \bar{b} are found by

$$q = (G^T G)^{-1} G^T z \quad (7)$$

For $G^T G$ to be nonsingular, we only require that at least one row of G is not a scalar multiple of another row. Practically, this means that the miniature AUV should not be stationary while collecting data for calibration.

A.3 On-line calibration example 1

The on-line least-squares gyro calibration method described in Section III-A.2 was tested using data collected in the laboratory. Figure 3 displays the true z-axis rotation of the AUV and the rotation of the AUV determined by integrating the gyro measurements with scale-factor and bias errors determined by (7). Gyro calibration coefficients are computed using raw uncorrected gyro data corresponding to Figure 3, $\bar{a} = -0.008528$ and $\bar{b} = -0.036459$. For this test, the AUV is placed on a lazy-Susan style platform and rotated to excite the gyro. The rotating platform is leveled with respect to horizontal to reduce additional error from pitch and roll measurements, $\phi = 0$ and $\theta = 0$. The true rotation of the AUV is determined by a shaft encoder temporarily mounted on the AUV.

During an actual deployment, the compass would be used to determine true z-axis rotation. But the electronic compass is highly susceptible to magnetic anomalies in the laboratory, including the effects of structure steel in the building, and an adequate calibration of the compass inside the laboratory was not possible. A detailed examination of the compass calibration problem is found in [4], and is not pursued here.

Fig. 3. True AUV heading and integrated/calibrated gyro measurements.

Calibration coefficients used for the data in Figure 3 are computed using raw data corresponding to Figure 3. Thus Figure 3 represents a least squares fit of the integrated gyro measurements to the true heading. Next, we assess

how well these calibration coefficients fit additional gyro measurements. Additional data showing true heading and integrated gyro measurements are shown in Figures 4 and 5. In Figure 5, the AUV is not rotated and the random-walk of the low-cost/low-accuracy gyro is clearly displayed.

Fig. 4. True AUV heading and integrated/calibrated gyro measurements with calibration coefficients determined from data shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 5. Integrated/calibrated gyro measurements when AUV is not rotating about z-axis.

A.4 On-line calibration example 2

To assess the on-line least squares algorithm in a more dynamic environment ($\phi(k) \neq 0, \theta(k) \neq 0$), we use a 5-link instructional robot arm to measure the orientation of the AUV through a series of trajectories. The AUV is mounted in the robot gripper and moved about the workspace. The orientation of the AUV is computed by applying the robot's forward kinematics to measured robot joint angles. We find a good match between pitch and roll determined via

the AUV's accelerometers and pitch and roll determined via the robot. Thus for the calibration algorithm, we use the AUV's measurements of pitch and roll; true heading is computed from robot forward kinematics.

Pitch and roll of the AUV as it moves through a prescribed trajectory is displayed in Figure 6. Figure 7 displays the true heading and the integrated gyro heading of the AUV during the same pitch and roll trajectory shown in Figure 6. Gyro calibration coefficients were computed using true heading and gyro data collected during this trajectory.

Fig. 6. Pitch and roll of the AUV while data is collected for on-line gyro calibration.

Fig. 7. True AUV heading and integrated/calibrated gyro measurements while AUV roll and pitch motions shown in Figure 6.

IV. COMPASS STABILIZATION

Once satisfactory calibration of the gyro is complete, the gyro can be used to stabilize heading measurements from the compass. In this section, we briefly describe our standard Kalman filter implementation for stabilizing the com-

pass. We have found in the laboratory that the electronic compass is highly susceptible to magnetic interference. In an operational context, we expect similar problems to arise when the miniature AUV is near the ship from which it is deployed, or near high permeability operational objectives. Thus we also examine Kalman filter-based methods for suppressing magnetic interference in the compass heading measurement.

A. Kalman filter-based compass stabilization

The Kalman filter is a well-known way to estimate true AUV heading despite noisy compass and gyro measurements. We briefly list the standard Kalman filter algorithm [3] adapted to the integral relationship between the compass and gyro shown in (4). The gyro and compass noise covariances are denoted Q and R , respectively.

1. Initialize: set $\hat{\psi}_{0|0} = E[\psi(0)]$ and $P_{0|0} = M_0$
2. Compute Kalman gain

$$K_k = \frac{P_{k|k-1}}{P_{k|k-1} + R}$$

3. Update prior estimate

$$\hat{\psi}_{k|k} = \hat{\psi}_{k|k-1} + K_k (y(k) - \hat{\psi}_{k|k-1})$$

4. Compute estimation error covariance

$$P_{k|k} = (1 - K_k) P_{k|k-1}$$

5. Predict ahead

$$\hat{\psi}_{k+1|k} = \hat{\psi}_{k|k} + h \frac{\cos \phi(k)}{\cos \theta(k)} (\bar{a}r_m(k) + \bar{b})$$

$$P_{k+1|k} = P_{k|k} + Q$$

6. Increment state estimate and error covariance estimate ($\hat{\psi}_{k+1|k} \mapsto \hat{\psi}_{k|k-1}$, $P_{k+1|k} \mapsto P_{k|k-1}$) and return to step 2.

B. Robustness to magnetic interference

We first examine the natural ability of the Kalman filter algorithm to reject magnetic interference seen in the compass measurements. To reject high frequency magnetic interference, we choose Q small and R large in the Kalman filter algorithm — indicating that we have more confidence in the gyro measurement than in the compass measurement. In Figure 8, the Kalman filter-based heading estimate is displayed against the true heading and also against the compass measurement. Small changes in the compass measurement with no corresponding change in the true heading are due to magnetic interference. For this data set $Q = 1.3$ degrees/sec and $R = 2000$ degrees. High frequency magnetic interference is clearly rejected. The limits of this approach is clearly shown in Figure 9 where lower frequency magnetic interference is not adequately rejected.

Fig. 8. Compass measurement and heading estimate (top), true heading and heading estimate (bottom). High frequency magnetic interference is rejected.

Fig. 9. Compass measurement and heading estimate (top), true heading and heading estimate (bottom). Lower frequency magnetic interference is not rejected.

There are a number of techniques for augmenting the Kalman filter to more successfully reject measurement anomalies such as magnetic interference [5], [6]. We choose to pursue a direct method in which the Kalman state update $\hat{\psi}_{k+1|k}$ is compared to the next compass measurement $y(k+1)$. If

$$|\hat{\psi}_{k+1|k} - y(k+1)| > \eta \quad (8)$$

where η is a constant, it is assumed that the compass is being influenced by magnetic interference, and step 3 in the Kalman filter algorithm is replaced by simply integrating the gyro measurement

$$\hat{\psi}_{k+1|k+1} = \hat{\psi}_{k|k} + h \frac{\cos \phi(k)}{\cos \theta(k)} (\bar{a}r_m(k) + \bar{b}) \quad (9)$$

Note that the all indexes in (9) should be reduced by one

to match notation in the Kalman filter algorithm.

Choosing $\eta = 2$ degrees, the data corresponding to Figure 9 is filtered using the magnetic interference test (8). The result is shown in Figure 10. The magnetic interference that was not rejected in Figure 9 is clearly rejected in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Compass measurement and heading estimate (top), true heading and heading estimate (bottom). Lower frequency magnetic interference is rejected.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The requirements of very small size and low cost for an autonomous underwater vehicle necessitate the use of small, inexpensive, and low-accuracy sensors. We have examined the utility of such sensors by specifically examining a small gyro and compass. We found that gyro calibration was variable and needed to be repeated periodically, and that the compass was highly susceptible to magnetic interference. Automatic calibration algorithms for the gyro were investigated and a least-squares solution was found suitable. Compass stabilization using the gyro was also investigated and a Kalman filter-based approach was adopted. Additional logic was added to the Kalman filter to detect and reject low-frequency magnetic interference.

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